

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF AGROCLUSTER MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. The article highlights that agro-clusters have significant potential for achieving high rates of agricultural production, economic and social development in rural areas, and that the further accelerated and sustainable development and modernization of the sector are directly linked to the competitiveness of fruit and vegetable growing.

Keywords: Fruits and vegetables, World economy, cluster, strategy, diversification, need, export, import, modernization, cooperation.

Agriculture occupies an important place in the economy of Uzbekistan, accounting for 25% of GDP, employing more than a quarter of the labor force of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan, in turn, not only meets the needs of its population, but also engages in the export of agricultural products and has great opportunities in this area.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. UP-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2019 No. PP-4239 "On Measures for the Development of Agricultural Cooperation in the Fruit and Vegetable Industry," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 11, 2019 No. PP-4549 "On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Fruit and Vegetable and Viticulture Industry, the Creation of a Value Chain in the Industry" are the main legislative acts that address the tasks facing this industry.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2018 No. UP-4947 "

Presidential Decree No. UP-5388 of October 23, 2019 "On Additional Measures for the Accelerated Development of Fruit and Vegetable Growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and

"On Approving the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030," as well as in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 17, 2018 No. PP-3978 "On Additional Measures to Increase the Efficiency of Promoting Fruit and Vegetable Products to Foreign Markets," dated November 23, 2021 No. PP-20 "On Measures for the Development of Family Entrepreneurship in Fruit and Vegetable Growing and Viticulture, Increasing the Share of Dehkan Farms in Agricultural Production," dated June 28, 2021.

The degree to which economic relations in the fruit and vegetable sector are organized in accordance with the requirements of a market economy determines the level of economic development of the fruit and vegetable sector and the economic efficiency of product cultivation. In market conditions, the increase in the volume and quality of fruit and vegetable production is primarily determined by the presence of market demand for the products being grown. Also, the quality of the product, the amount of resources spent on its cultivation,

stimulate changes in the volume of demand in the market. Therefore, in fruit and vegetable farms, there is a growing need for scientifically based placement of varieties of fruit and vegetable crops that meet the requirements of the domestic and foreign markets, corresponding to the natural and climatic conditions of each region with high early maturity, yield, and consumer quality.

The purpose of forming clusters is to orient enterprises of the same industry located within the city, district, and region and harmonizing educational, scientific, engineering, consulting, standardization, certification, application of innovative technologies, and other services in a single technological chain with them to create competitive goods based on the organization of innovative production.

One of the pressing problems of the modern world is ensuring food security and food security of countries.

Agroclusters and state policy:

Many countries support the development of agro-clusters, as this contributes to the modernization of agriculture and the strengthening of the rural economy. Financial assistance, education, and training will be organized through state programs.

Thanks to the significant work carried out in this direction in recent years, the common interests of producers and processors of products using the cluster method are ensured. Cluster participants are taking the initiative to solve the accumulated problems in the industry by bringing industry to rural areas. Most importantly, clusters provide employment for people, who work year-round and receive a monthly salary.

The activities of the agro-cluster are carried out in the following areas:

- based on the study of advanced foreign experience in fruit and vegetable growing, their wide use in regional conditions, as well as attracting foreign specialists to the introduction of the cluster system in the fruit and vegetable industry;
- production of agricultural products that fully meet the requirements of the foreign market, development and further development of their selection and seed production in the country;
- it is recommended to introduce a system that fully covers the process of planting high-yielding fruit and vegetable crops, growing, storing, processing and selling products, as well as modern innovative, resource-saving technologies into the process of growing fruit and vegetable products and compliance with phytosanitary rules.

Figure 1. Founders of the cluster.

The issue of forming clusters in the textile and light industry of Uzbekistan is extremely relevant, and its positive solution is expedient to form on a national scale in a vertical and horizontal system, based on determining the socio-economic conditions of the regions, the competitive environment and clustering opportunities, as well as in regions where specialized education and science are developing.

There are problems in the regulation of agro-clusters. The issues of accelerated development of agriculture, increasing its economic efficiency, improving the living conditions of the rural population, and ensuring their interest are connected with the modern method of production in the industry - the cluster system. However, the experience of the past period shows that there are a number of problems in the legal regulation of clusters.

Including:

- the legal status of the agro-industrial cluster is not defined, that is, regulatory legal acts do not contain the status of the agro-industrial cluster, its criteria and grounds for liquidation;
- there is no unified approach to the organization of agro-industrial clusters.
- fruit and vegetable clusters are established on the basis of a trilateral agreement concluded between the initiator, local government bodies and the Ministry of Agriculture, rice-growing clusters - on the basis of a bilateral agreement concluded between the initiator and local government bodies;
- relations between agro-industrial clusters and the state are not regulated;
- there is a practice of mandatory assignment of farms to agro-industrial clusters;
- there is no unified approach to the allocation of land plots to agro-industrial clusters;
- there is no system for the formation of agricultural cooperatives, which will be the main impetus for the development of agro-clusters;
- mental (psychological) unpreparedness for establishing cooperative relations and free association, lack of self-management skills in economic management;

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CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSALS. Economic growth of the fruit and vegetable sector should not be achieved by further expanding the use of existing domestic resources, but by introducing a system of competitive production cooperation and clusters that meet modern requirements in terms of product quality.

For the sustainable development of the industry in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is advisable to pay attention to:

- further strengthening of financial incentives for the activities of exemplary enterprises operating in rural areas, directly specializing in the innovative resource-saving storage and processing of agricultural products, introducing tax, customs, and other benefits for them;
- the creation of export-credit organizations or assigning the solution of these issues to the responsible ministries and departments in order to provide comprehensive practical assistance to the entrepreneur in issues of pre-export lending, insurance, occupying a place in foreign markets, "geographical, economic, financial and qualitative risks," transport and logistics, obtaining appropriate certificates, food security (FSA), and standards, ensuring participation in international exhibitions and fairs;
- Implementation of the "Fruit and Vegetable Clinic" service.

Bibliographic list:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Meva-sabzavotchilik va uzumchilik tarmog'ini yanada rivojlantirish, sohada qo'shilgan qiymat zanjirini yaratishga doir qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ-4549-son qarori
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 23-oktabrdagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirishning 2020-2030 yillarga mo'ljallangan strategiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi PF-5853-son Farmoni.
3. G.M.Olimjonova & Juraboyev M. (2023). Agriculture development in our country. International Conference On Higher Education Teaching,1(3), 26–30. Retrieved from <http://aidlix.com/index.php/de/article/view/490>
4. Olimjonova, G.M. "Fermer xo'jaligida meva yetishtirish bo'yicha xorij tajribalarining ahamiyati". www.miastoprzyszlosci.com.
5. Olimjonova G.M. & O.Shermatov "Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda meva-sabzavotchilik sohasining o'rni". Ilmiy amaliy agroiqtsodiy jurnal.2(20)2021.UDK:663/664:634
6. Olimjonova G.M. & Boqijonov Sarvarbek Adxamjon o'g'li "Fermer xo'jaliklarida meva yetishtirish holati, rivojlantirish hamda diversifikatsiyalash samaradorligi". "International scientific and technical conference on the topic of the scientific and practical foundations of the effective use of resource-saving innovative technologies in agriculture" 27-28 October 2023. № 315339-341-sahifalar.
7. Olimjonova G.M. & Sobirova Yu. "Improving the economic mechanism of intensive horticulture development " . Volume 4/ Feb 2023. ISSN:2795-5621 Available:<http://procedia.online/index.php/applied/index>.

8. Olimjonova, G.M. & Rasulova Zilolaxon "The significance of citrus fruits grown in the republic of uzbekistan in the national economy" Spanish Journal of Innovation and INTEGRITY.ISSN:/2792-8268.Volume:25, Dec-2023.<http://indexedresearch.org>.
9. Olimjonova,G.M. "Competitiveness of the Fruit and Vegetable sector in the Food Network" Journal of Marketing and Emerging Economics /e-ISSN:2792-4009/www.openaccessjournals.eu/ Volume:3 Issue 12
10. Olimjonova,G.M. "O'zbekiston respublikasida meva-sabzavot mahsulotlari eksporti salohiyatini iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili" Хоразм Маъмун академияси ахборотномаси: илмий журнал.-№12/2(109),Хоразм Маъмун академияси,2023 й.-280 б.-Босма нашрнинг электрон варианты-<http://mamun.uz/uz/page/56>. ISSN 2091-573X